

**STUDENTS' PERCEPTION ABOUT INCLUSION OF CHHATRAPATI
SHIVAJI MAHARAJ'S THOUGHTS AND PRACTICES IN CURRICULUM
OF MANAGEMENT - A STUDY FOCUSED ON DEGREE COLLEGE
STUDENTS IN KALYAN DOMBIVILI REGION.**

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Management is pervasive. It is applicable in all walks of life. As far as higher education is concerned, most of the management lessons, thoughts, theories and principles that are taught in higher educational institutions are predominantly of foreign authors. Maharashtra has a varied heritage in a plethora of areas. One of the most important being Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj who established 'Swarajya' & laid down several plans, policies, and procedures for its strategic management. As far as higher education is concerned i.e., graduation and post-graduation, there are hardly any subjects or syllabus which include Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj's thoughts and practices in Management. To study the perception of Students towards the inclusion of Shivaji Maharaj thoughts and practices a study was conducted in the Kalyan Dombivili region. The study consisted of both Primary as well as Secondary data. The Primary data was collected from students as well as parents in Kalyan Dombivili region through a Structured Questionnaire using a 5-point Likert Scale. The Null Hypotheses were tested using the non-Parametric test, Mann-Whitney U test and the findings are presented in research paper. The present paper will be useful to Students, Universities as suggestions are given towards the implementation of thoughts and practices of Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj in the syllabus of Management.

Key words : *Management, Strategic Management, Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj, Generation Y & Generation Z, Curriculum, Higher Education*

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Introduction :

Most of the management lessons, thoughts, theories and principles of foreign authors are used while teaching the subject of management across higher educational institutions. India has a legacy of different Kings who were great warriors and have demonstrated crucial lessons of Management through their working style towards day to day functioning of their kingdom.

When we look back at glorious history of Maharashtra especially the managerial skills demonstrated by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj not only the way he handled his people but also the way he managed his day-to-day administration in smooth manner. Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj's government had already used concepts like 'Ashtapradhan Mandal' now known as 'Cabinet'. Maharaj had pioneered war tactic of 'Ganimi Kava' also known as 'Guerrilla warfare'. The present research paper is an attempt to evaluate the perception of stakeholders about inclusion of 'Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj's' thoughts and practices in curriculum of management.

Review of Literature :

Hattangadi (2020) in her online blog on "Shivaji Maharaj the greatest management strategist" expressed foresightedness as an important quality of Maharaj due to ability of Maharaj to think ahead of time. At the same time Maharaj was truly a secular leader giving due respect to all the religion at the same time Maharaj gave due respect to women. Maharaj was one of the few leaders who had set up intelligence bureau to study the strategies used by enemies in order to prepare an effective counterattack.

Parrkhi (2018) in his research article on "Shivaj Maharaj and his management skills" stated different managerial skills possessed by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj like administration, foresightedness, rational decision making, communication skills along with the ability to earn loyal set of followers. It was found plans and policies framed by Shivaji Maharaj were quite modern and most of the principles preached by Maharaj are even applicable today.

Hari and Hari (2018) in their research paper titled "Shivaji Maharaj: An Indian Management Legend" stated Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj established a working pattern in which the King was the custodian of common people. Maharaj reawakened youth's hidden abilities thereby building self-assurance in them and taught them to fight against the foreign forces in order to maintain value of life. Shivaji Maharaj's enemies were well-equipped with arms and ammunition along with huge amount of funding however Maharaj conquered his formidable foes with the basic available meagre resources and the bravery portrayed by his loyal disciples.

Gonda and Parab (2013) in their book titled "Leadership Learning from Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj" focused on leadership lessons demonstrated by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj. It was found Maharaj was a true visionary and an ideal leader with the ability to bring together people and eradicate the barrier of religion and cast. Leadership skills of Maharaj are truly applicable for today's young generation as they can learn the principles of team work and strong people management which is the need of hour.

Objectives :

1. To know about the concept of Swarajya laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.
2. To analyze the perception of students and parents towards subject of Management education.
3. To analyze the perception of students and parents towards learning thoughts and practice laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.

Hypotheses :

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Gender and perception towards Management education.

H_1 : There is significant difference between Gender and perception towards Management education.

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Gender and thoughts & practices laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.

H_1 : There is significant difference between Gender and thoughts & practices laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Stakeholders and perception towards Management education.

H_1 : There is significant difference between Stakeholders and perception towards Management education.

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Stakeholders and thoughts & practices laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.

H_1 : There is significant difference between Stakeholders and thoughts & practices laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.

Research Methodology :

The research study is indicative and analytical in nature. Both primary and secondary data was collected. Primary data was collected by floating structured questionnaire through google form among both students as well as parents across Kalyan Dombivili region. The questionnaire was framed with five-point Likert scale. The secondary data was collected from books, articles, research papers, blogs and websites. The sample size for the study consisted of parents and students in Kalyan Dombivili region. Convenience Sampling Method was used for Data collection. The questionnaire was subject to editing. Data was classified, tabulated and summarized in the flow of paper.

Limitations of Study :

1. The study is restricted to Kalyan Dombivili region.
2. Time is a constraint to meet more number of parents and students.

Data Analysis :

The data analysis was done by using S.P.S.S. The normality test was conducted to check normality of data by using Kolmogorov-Smirnov & Shapiro-Wilk test. The data was found to be non-normal hence null hypotheses were tested by using non-parametric test i.e., Mann-Whitney U Test.

Normality testing :

Normality of data was tested using Kolmogorov-Smirnov & Shapiro-Wilk test.

H_0 : Distribution is Normal

H_1 : Distribution is non-Normal

Table 1
Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Perception towards Management Education	.168	65	.000	.940	65	.003
Thoughts and practices laid down by Shivaji Maharaj	.168	65	.000	.891	65	.000

Source: Primary data

The table number 1 indicated significant value for the variables were less than 0.05 which means the Null Hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted that is distribution is non-Normal hence appropriate non-Parametric test Mann-Whitney U test was used for further analysis.

Testing of Null Hypotheses

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Gender and perception towards Management education.

H_1 : There is significant difference between Gender and perception towards Management education.

Table 2
Mann-Whitney U Test - Gender and perception towards Management education.

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
There is no significant difference between Gender and perception towards Management education	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.358	Retain the null hypothesis.

Source: Primary data

The Table number 2 indicated that the significant value is 0.358 which is greater than 0.05 thereby indicating the null hypothesis is accepted that means There is no significant difference between Gender and perception towards Management education.

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Stakeholders and perception towards Management education.

H_1 : There is significant difference between Stakeholders and perception towards Management education.

Table 3

Mann-Whitney U Test - Stakeholder and perception towards Management education.

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
There is no significant difference between Stakeholders and perception towards Management education	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.295	Retain the null hypothesis.

Source: Primary data

The Table number 3 indicated that significant value is 0.295 which is greater than 0.05 thereby indicating the null hypothesis is accepted that means There is no significant difference between Stakeholders and perception towards Management education.

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Gender and thoughts & practices laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.

H_1 : There is significant difference between Gender and thoughts & practices laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.

Table 4

Mann-Whitney U Test - Gender and thoughts & practice laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
There is no significant difference between Gender and thoughts & practices laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.786	Retain the null hypothesis.

Source: Primary data

The Table number 4 indicated that significant value is 0.786 which is greater than 0.05 thereby indicating the null hypothesis is accepted that means There is no significant difference between Gender and thoughts & practice laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Stakeholders and thoughts & practices laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.

H₁: There is significant difference between Stakeholders and thoughts & practices laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.

Table 5

Mann-Whitney U Test - Stakeholders and thoughts & practice laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
There is no significant difference between Stakeholders and thoughts & practices laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.480	Retain the null hypothesis.

Source: Primary data

The Table number 5 indicated that significant value is 0.480 which is greater than 0.05 thereby indicating the null hypothesis is accepted that means There is no significant difference between Stakeholders and thoughts & practice laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.

Findings of the Study

1. Out of the total respondents 58.5% were Male while 41.5% were Female. 70.8% of the Stakeholder were students while 29.2% were Parents.
2. It was found that irrespective of Gender and Stakeholders perception towards the subject of management education and thoughts & practices laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj was same.
3. Out of the total respondents 67.7% agreed management theories, thoughts, principles of foreign authors are taught in classroom-based teaching. 81.5% stated curriculum of management needs to be changed & can include learnings of Indian Management Guru.
4. 70.7% agreed that while achieving the vision of 'Swarajya' as a part of strategic management, 'Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj, has laid down number of plans, policies and procedures.

Discussions :

In this study, it was found that irrespective of gender there is a positive perception towards implementation of Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj's thoughts and practices in the curriculum of Management. It is one of the indicators which states the clear need to conduct further studies towards its practical implementation. Further studies may be undertaken to study the perception of other stakeholders like teachers, parents, administrative experts in the field of Management towards implementing thoughts and practices led down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj in Management curriculum. After studying the perception of the stakeholders, there might be a need to formalize the theories laid down by Maharaj across different streams as a part of the curriculum.

Suggestions :

1. A reference book may be published focusing on thoughts, practices, theories, principles of management demonstrated by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj.
2. Strategies laid down by Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj while laying down the foundation of 'Swarajya' may be included as a case study in curriculum of management education.
3. Principles and practices formulated by Indian Management gurus may be drafted in formulating the curriculum of management education.
4. Workshops may be organised in association with board of studies so as to include thoughts and practices of Maharaj across higher education.
5. Different subjects may be introduced on principles preached by Maharaj like Asthapradhan (Management), Balutedar (Finance), Gainimkava (Strategic Management)
6. Keeping in mind the transdisciplinary approach recommended by the National Education policy preaching of Maharaj may not be restricted only to subject of History for the students of Arts but for students from other streams too where in subjects related to general administration, Financial management may be taught to students from the preaching given by Maharaj.

Significance of Study :

The study identified that there is a change needed in the curriculum of management and include learnings of Indian management guru. Keeping in mind the competition at the same time matching the curriculum of international universities this will take time. The present study is significant to the Universities as suggestion is given towards use of 'Swarajya' as a case study while framing the curriculum of management education. It will be significant to budding authors who wish to write reference books on Shivaji Maharaj and his practices. It will be significant to students and society at large as it would help in adhering to the learnings from Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj as an Indian Management Guru.

Conclusion :

"Management is about arranging and telling. Leadership is about nurturing and enhancing." Maharashtra has a prestigious history wherein visionary leader like 'Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj' demonstrated effective Managerial skills while working towards establishing 'Swarajya'. It is the need of the hour to teach thoughts and practices of Indian management gurus to our students rather than just teaching them the tried and tested theories. It will be quite easy for the student community to co-relate the management principles, theories, thoughts and practices, if demonstrated through series of historical events involving management guru like 'Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj'. Students would definitely leverage on these historic events and its significance in understanding and applying management thoughts and practices in every course of life.

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